

Golay Waveforms and Adaptive Estimation

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Abstract—An iterative range profile estimation process is derived for Golay waveforms. The Re-Iterative Super Resolution (RISR) algorithm is used in conjunction with Golay waveforms and processing for radar range-Doppler estimation. Various additional range-Doppler estimation methods that use RISR and Golay waveforms and processing are simulated for the sake of comparison. Range and Doppler sidelobes are seen in simulation to be mitigated to a significant extent by using RISR in conjunction with Golay waveforms and processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern radar and other active sensors, a signal is transmitted, directed into an associated medium such as free space in radar, and reflected back to a receiver by any scatterers. The delays associated with reflected signals arriving at the receiver provide a spatial profile associated with the respective ranges to the scatterers.

In radar, the high-power narrow-pulse transmissions required to achieve high range resolutions are often limited by practical power constraints. To overcome such limits, transmitted radar signals often take the form of a phase or frequency modulated rectangular pulse to obtain high spatial resolution inversely proportional to the modulation bandwidth in a technique known as pulse compression [7]. The received signal consists of delayed, attenuated versions of the transmitted waveform. A filter matched to the transmitted waveform extracts the high-resolution spatial profile from the received signal.

For a solitary point scatterer in the presence of white Gaussian noise, the matched filter (i.e., matched to the transmitted signal and system noise) maximizes the output signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and hence the detectability of the scatterer. The matched filter correlates the delayed, attenuated versions of the transmitted waveform as they arrive at the receiver and provides the range and relative complex amplitudes of scatterers. The correlation of the matched filter with the waveform is the autocorrelation of the waveform. However, an inherent problem is the masking of small targets by large nearby targets due to range sidelobes that are present when using the standard matched filtering method.

Blunt and Gerlach [1] developed a method for range profile estimation, Adaptive Pulse Compression (APC), in which a filter adapted to the scene is derived for each range bin. Each filter is optimally adapted to its respective range cell based on the minimum mean-square error (MMSE) criterion [4]. Consequently, range sidelobes of targets are mitigated to a large extent. The problem of range sidelobes can alternatively

be addressed by utilizing complementary Golay waveforms. For example, Searle et al. [6] develops a Golay waveform approach that involves frequency separating Golay coded pulses and nonlinear signal processing. An alternative Golay waveform approach involves the transmission of particular sequences of Golay waveforms [5].

In this paper, an iterative range profile estimation technique is developed for Golay waveforms. Additionally, this Golay processing technique is used in conjunction with the RISR algorithm for range-Doppler estimation. The resulting estimated range Doppler maps are seen in simulation to exhibit low Doppler sidelobes as well as low range sidelobes.

II. RANGE DOPPLER MAP ESTIMATION VIA RANGE PROFILE ESTIMATION IN CONJUNCTION WITH RISR PROCESSING FOR DOPPLER ESTIMATION

In this section, the RISR algorithm is described in the context of utilizing it in conjunction with a range profile estimation algorithm for the purpose of range Doppler estimation. For example, RISR could be used in conjunction with either APC, matched filter processing, or iterative Golay processing. In this paper, matched filter processing and iterative Golay processing are considered. Assume that a number of pulses are coherently transmitted and that the corresponding radar returns are collected. From this data, a range Doppler map is estimated by first estimating the range profiles corresponding to the transmitted pulses, and then, for each range cell, applying the RISR algorithm to the corresponding values from each estimated range profile.

In [2], the RISR algorithm was developed in the context of direction-of-arrival estimation. However, here we apply it to the problem of Doppler estimation by feeding a different input to it and interpreting the output differently. The actual RISR algorithm used here for Doppler estimation is virtually identical to the algorithm described in [2]. However, the signal model assumed for the received data is different.

Assume that N pulses are transmitted, and that data from L range bins are collected for each pulse. Let \mathbb{C} denote the complex numbers. Assume the range Doppler map to be estimated is denoted by $\mathbf{x}(1), \mathbf{x}(2), \dots, \mathbf{x}(L)$ where $\mathbf{x}(l) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and each $x_m(l)$ represents the point scatterer corresponding to Doppler bin m ($1 \leq m \leq M$) and range l ($1 \leq l \leq L$). In order to match the notation of [2], define

$$\mathbf{y}(l) = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{x}(l)$$

where each element $s_{n,m}$ of the $N \times M$ matrix \mathbf{S} is given by $s_{n,m} = \exp(iq_{n,m})$ and each $q_{n,m}$ is an element of the matrix

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & \dots & N-1 \\ -\pi & -\pi + \frac{2\pi}{M-1} & \dots & \pi - \frac{2\pi}{M-1} & \pi \end{bmatrix}^T.$$

For notational convenience, for each $1 \leq n \leq N$, denote the range profile associated with pulse n as

$$\mathbf{u}_n = [y_n(1) \ y_n(2) \ \dots \ y_n(L)]^T.$$

The signal model for the received data is then given by

$$\mathbf{z}_n = \mathbf{s} * \mathbf{u}_n + \mathbf{v}_n.$$

where \mathbf{v}_n is independent identically distributed (i. i. d.) Gaussian noise and the asterick $*$ denotes convolution. In this paper, two methods will be considered for estimating the range profiles \mathbf{u}_n : standard matched filter processing, and iterative Golay processing. Denote by $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_n$ the estimate for \mathbf{u}_n obtained by one of these two methods. Again, to match the notation of [2], for $1 \leq l \leq L$, define

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(l) = [\hat{u}_1(l) \ \hat{u}_2(l) \ \dots \ \hat{u}_N(l)]^T.$$

This estimated data is used as input to the RISR algorithm. Specifically, as in [2], the initial estimate is given by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0(l) = \mathbf{S}^H \hat{\mathbf{y}}(l)$, and the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k(l)$ is computed iteratively by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}(l) = \bar{\mathbf{W}}_k^H(l) \mathbf{y}(l)$ where element (n,m) of the $N \times M$ matrix $\bar{\mathbf{W}}_k(l)$ is given by

$$\bar{w}_k(l)^{(n,m)} = \frac{w_k(l)^{(n,m)}}{\sum_{1 \leq n \leq N} w_k(l)^{(n,m)} s^{(n,m)}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_k(l) = (\mathbf{S} \mathbf{P}_k(l) \mathbf{S}^H + \mathbf{R})^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{P}_k(l),$$

$\mathbf{P}_k(l)$ is the $M \times M$ diagonal matrix whose elements are those of the diagonal of $\mathbf{x}_k(l) \mathbf{x}_k^H(l)$, and \mathbf{R} is a $N \times N$ diagonal matrix of noise covariances.

A derivation \mathbf{R} based on the signal model and range profile estimation process used is not undertaken. For the purposes of the simulations of this paper, \mathbf{R} is set to be equal to $\text{diag}(\{0.0001\}^N)$. It should also be noted that equation (1) is a normalization step that was not included in [2]; including it has been observed to improve the performance of the RISR algorithm.

III. ITERATIVE RANGE PROFILE ESTIMATION FOR GOLAY WAVEFORMS

Let the vector \mathbf{x} represent the range profile of a radar target scene that is to be estimated. Let $(\mathbf{s}_a, \mathbf{s}_b)$ be a Golay pair. Consider the transmission of the signal \mathbf{s}_a . Let the received signal \mathbf{y} be modelled as

$$\mathbf{y} = g(\mathbf{x} * \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{v})$$

where g is an unknown gain and \mathbf{v} is a vector of independent identically distributed Gaussian noise. For notational convenience, let $\bar{*}$ denote the convolution operator that is such that $\dim(\mathbf{a} \bar{*} \mathbf{b}) = \max\{\dim(\mathbf{a}), \dim(\mathbf{b})\}$. That is, assuming that

$\dim(\mathbf{a}) \leq \dim(\mathbf{b})$, the k^{th} element of the convolution $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{a} \bar{*} \mathbf{b}$, for $1 \leq k \leq \dim(\mathbf{b}) - \dim(\mathbf{a}) + 1$ is given by

$$c_k = \sum_{j=1}^{\dim(\mathbf{a})} a_j b_{k-j+\dim(\mathbf{a})}.$$

For any vector \mathbf{q} , denote by \mathbf{q}^{R*} the conjugate of the vector whose elements are those of \mathbf{q} in reverse order. Also, denote by $\max(\mathbf{q})$ the maximum value of the magnitudes of the elements of \mathbf{q} . Define $f: \mathbb{C}^{\dim(\mathbf{y})} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{\dim(\mathbf{y})}$ by

$$f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{s}_a^{R*} \bar{*} \mathbf{y} \frac{1}{\max(\mathbf{y})} + \mathbf{s}_b^{R*} \bar{*} \mathbf{s}_b * \hat{\mathbf{x}} \frac{1}{\max(\mathbf{s}_b \bar{*} \hat{\mathbf{x}})}.$$

Let the estimate of the range profile $\check{\mathbf{x}}$ be given by $\check{\mathbf{x}} = \max(\mathbf{y}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}$ where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is the solution to the equation

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}).$$

This equation can be solved numerically by iteratively applying f . That is, let $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ be given by $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbf{s}_a \mathbf{y}$. Then compute $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k)$ until a convergence criterion is satisfied. The convergence of the algorithm is a topic for future research, although in the simulations conducted it was observed to converge.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Various combinations of methods for range profile estimation and Doppler estimation are simulated. The methods for range profile estimation considered are standard matched filter processing and iterative Golay processing. The methods for Doppler estimation are the FFT algorithm and the RISR algorithm. Additionally, a method for range Doppler map estimation is simulated in which the RISR algorithm is applied first, directly to the received data, with Golay processing performed subsequently. The simulations were done using an 8-bit Golay code. The number of range cells simulated was 1000, the number of Doppler bins assumed and estimated was 120, and the number of transmitted pulses was 50. Finally, it should be noted that the Golay processed pulses were all normalized by the same factor so that the maximum magnitude over all pulses and range cells was 1. The SNR of the raw received radar return was set to about 0 dB.

Figure 1 shows the ground truth range Doppler map. In addition to clutter around the zero Doppler axis, a large clutter patch with positive Doppler is also included. Figure 2 shows the range Doppler map estimate resulting from standard Doppler processing consisting of a matched filter followed by an FFT. The range Doppler map clearly exhibits both range and Doppler sidelobes. In particular, sidelobes from the positive Doppler clutter patch are apparent in the range-Doppler space directly above it.

Using matched filtering followed by RISR processing results in a reduction in Doppler sidelobes; Figure 3 shows the range Doppler map estimate resulting from the standard matched filter followed by RISR processing. Figures 4 and 5 show cuts of Figure 3 along the swaths shown in Figure 6. Note that in these and all subsequent range and Doppler cut figures, the

Fig. 1. Ground truth range-Doppler map.

Fig. 2. MF-FFT - Estimated range Doppler map resulting from matched filter processing followed by FFT processing.

Fig. 3. MF-RISR - Estimated range Doppler map resulting from matched filter processing followed by RISR.

Fig. 4. MF-RISR - Range cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from matched filter processing followed by RISR.

lines and points across the tops of the figures indicate the true range and Doppler supports. The Doppler sidelobes are mitigated quite significantly, as evidenced by the clear “columns” of space surrounding the two clutter patches in Figure 3. However, range sidelobes remain, as evidenced by the “noise” above the clutter patch to the right in Figure 3.

Figure 7 shows the estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by the FFT. Figures 8 and 9 show cuts of Figure 7 along the swaths shown in Figure 6. In contrast to the previous MF-RISR case, the range sidelobes, even those from the large clutter patch, are mitigated significantly, as can be seen in Figure 8. While in the MF-RISR case Doppler sidelobes were mitigated, here Doppler sidelobes from the two clutter patches are apparent throughout the estimated range Doppler map.

Figure 10 shows the range Doppler map estimate resulting from Golay processing followed by RISR processing. Figures 11 and 12 show cuts of Figure 10 along the swaths shown in

Figure 6. Here, both range sidelobes and Doppler sidelobes are mitigated significantly.

Figure 13 shows the range Doppler map estimate resulting from RISR processing the received data first, and then performing Golay processing on the resulting Doppler separated received data. In this case, significant range sidelobes from the positive Doppler clutter patch are apparent, as evidenced by the “noise” above this clutter patch in Figure 13. Doppler sidelobes are mitigated to some extent.

V. CONCLUSION

The RISR algorithm was used in conjunction with Golay waveforms and an iterative Golay processing algorithm for radar range-Doppler estimation. The Golay-RISR method was shown in simulation to be very promising for estimating range Doppler maps in highly cluttered environments. Additionally, the Golay-FFT method can be seen to be particularly effective

Fig. 5. MF-RISR - Doppler cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from matched filter processing followed by RISR.

Fig. 6. Range and Doppler cut swaths.

in mitigating range sidelobes. Finally, the MF-RISR method was also effective in recovering the range Doppler map from the simulated radar data, but with some range sidelobes remaining.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. D. Blunt and K. Gerlach, "Adaptive Pulse Compression via MMSE Estimation," *IEEE Trans. on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, Vol. 42, No. 2, pp. 572-583, April 2006.
- [2] S. D. Blunt, T. Chan, and K. Gerlach, "A New Framework for Direction-of-Arrival Estimation," *IEEE Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop*, pp. 81-85, Darmstadt, Germany, July 21-23, 2008.
- [3] T. Higgins, S. D. Blunt, and A. K. Shackelford, "Space-Range Adaptive Processing for Waveform-Diverse Radar Imaging," *IEEE Radar Conference*, pp. 321-326, May 10-14, 2010.
- [4] S.M. Kay, *Fundamentals of Statistical Signal Processing: Estimation Theory*, Upper Saddle River, NJ, Prentice-Hall, 1993, pp. 219-286 and pp. 344-350.

Fig. 7. Golay-FFT - Estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by FFT processing.

Fig. 8. Golay-FFT - Range cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by FFT processing.

- [5] A. Pezeshki, A. R. Calderbank, W. Moran, and S. D. Howard, "Doppler Resilient Golay Complementary Waveforms," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, Vol. 54, No. 9, pp. 4254-4266, September 2008.
- [6] S. J. Searle, S. D. Howard, and W. Moran, "Formation of Ambiguity Functions with Frequency-Separated Golay Coded Pulses," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, Vol. 45, No. 4, pp. 1580-1597, October 2009.
- [7] M. I. Skolnik, *Introduction to Radar Systems*, (3rd ed.), New York, McGraw-Hill, 2001, pp. 339-369.

Fig. 9. Golay-FFT - Doppler cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by FFT processing.

Fig. 12. Golay-RISR - Doppler cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by RISR.

Fig. 10. Golay-RISR - Estimated range Doppler Map resulting from Golay processing followed by RISR.

Fig. 11. Golay-RISR - Range cut of estimated range Doppler map resulting from Golay processing followed by RISR.

Fig. 13. RISR-Golay - Estimated range Doppler map resulting from RISR followed by Golay processing.